

Contributory Pension Scheme and Management of Retirement Benefits in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka: An Ethical Appraisal

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Abstract

Conventionally, the upsurge in the level of impoverishment experienced by retirees in the recent decades in both public and private sectors in mostly fused cum prismatic societies has exacerbated following the reluctant abdication of duties and obligatory roles bequeathed to the state via the social contract. Recently, in many developing societies, the state has ethically failed to provide the needed social safety nets for her citizens to enjoy even against those working to see that the day to day affairs of the state are systematically carried out. However, it is at this juncture that the paper consciously set to ethically investigate and at the same time interrogates the voluntary pension contribution and welfare of Retirees and ways of improving the retirement benefits of retirees using University of Nigeria, Nsukka as case study. Data were collected from the University of Nigeria Bursary Department, Pension Fund Administrators and Pension Commission (PENCOM). The paper utilized qualitative method in generating data and it was anchored on Marxian instrumentalist theory to explicate that the New contributory pension scheme is a product designed through the doctrine and practices of Neo-liberal policy, which helps the state through its agency to abdicate its fundamental roles. The findings revealed that there is a marked departure in the retirement benefits of retirees in the old and new pension schemes, with the retirees in the new contributory scheme receiving lower benefits than before. However, the study recommends the right to gratuity and pension for life for public servants and a comprehensive accounting standard for retirement benefits be seriously put in place to protect the pension funds

Key Words: Contributory Pension, Defined Benefits Scheme, Pension System, Pension Retirement Benefits, and University of Nigeria.

Introduction

Pension system and administration has become a reoccurring issue over the centuries following the adoption of the Elizabethan law of 1648. In the contemporary time in many diffracted cum prismatic societies, pension system has significantly attracted greater attentions of policy makers and other relevant stakeholders. However, pension administration in Nigeria is not an exception. The origination of the scheme in the Nigeria public service was the product or efforts of the Native administrative servants. This could be dated back in 1946 when the colonial government through the chief secretary to the government issued a circular numbered 19/1945 of 24th March, 1945 announcing the commencement of pension scheme in Africa for her staff.

However, the colonial policy statement received a significant and appropriate legal backing and enactment following the introduction and subsequent implementation of the pension ordinance of 1951 which took retroactive effect from 1946 (Odo, Igbeka & Ani, 2011). According to Odia and Okoye, (2012); Owujori, (2008), they argued that the contents of the 1946 pension ordinance were not clear and understandable to the Native Administrators. They maintained that the 1946 ordinance contained confused information to whom is a native administrator, the nature of benefits and eligibility for either pension or gratuity. This clearly points that under the 1946 pension ordinance, pension rights is not for Native Administrators but was discriminately used by Governor – general's discretion.

To address the inadequacies and complications inherent in the 1946 ordinance, an indigenous Pension Act was initiated following the gaining of the flag independence by Nigeria in 1960. The new Pension Act was enacted in 1979 with the legal backing Number 102 of 1979. It also took retroactive effect from 1st of April, 1974. However, the 1979 Pension Act significantly became the fundamental pension law upon which other pension

laws in both public and private sectors were adequately emerged. However, pension scheme in any social formation has always remained a form of social security and safety nets, an instrument for enhancing livelihood in a society by ensuring that workers enjoy an appreciable level of welfare after retirement (Nwabueze, 1989; Ogwunike, 2008; Nwafor, 2009; Okotoni & Akeredolu, 2006).

Furthermore, it is more appreciable to note that under the 1979 Pension Act, pension and gratuity became the rights of the qualified employees. This is provided for by the 1979, 1989 and 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, section 210(1) and (2) adequately stated that:

“the right of a person in the public service of a state to receive pension or gratuity shall be regulated by law. Any benefit to which a person is entitled in accordance with or under such law as is referred to in subsection(1) of this section shall not be withheld or altered to his disadvantages except to such extent as it permissible under any law, including the code of conduct”

However, in the private sector, pension administration was adequately administered and maintained through the institution of National Provident Fund (NPF) which was the first formal pension scheme in Nigeria and was established in 1961 for private sector employers. In 1993, the NPF was replaced with Nigeria Social Insurance Trust Fund (NSITF) set up by Decree No 73 of 1993 which later commenced operation in 1994. The nature and operation of NSITF was more of contributory order than defined by both the employees and the employers (Aborisade, 2012; Amoo, 2008; Kenechukwu & Ugwu, 2011; Daze & Nyong, 2011).

Consequently, the Federal Government on its unthwarted effort decided to embark on a reform of the pension scheme and administration by emulating the Chilean pension system which was implemented and adjudged the best in 1981. The reform introduced a contributory pension scheme which is a complete paradigm shift with the old Pay As You Go (PAYG) system (Onyeonuru, Egharevba & Imhonopi, 2013, Elekwa, Koh and Ugwu, 2011). This shiftability to contributory pension regime informed the Nigeria pension as were enshrined in the Pension reform Act, 2004 (Now Pension Reform Act, 2014) of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The Act specifies the contributory rate of the new scheme to be a minimum of 15% (Now 18% under the 2014 Pension Reform Act) of the employee's emolument made up of minimum 7.5% (Now 10%) from the employer and 7.5 (Now 8%) from the employee in the case of the public service of the federation (PRA, 2014: 35). Conventionally, the reform is aimed at neglecting the needs to improve the retirement benefits of retirees. It also expresses and propagates the basis of neoliberal agenda of relieving the state through its agency the government, the responsibilities of catering for the elderly in the society. Importantly, it aimed adequately to benefit and empower the ruling capitalist class at the expenses of the proletariat, thereby making funds available for investment and stimulating the capital market at detriment workers (Amoo, 2008; Ogwunike 2000; Aborisade, 2012).

2. Theoretical Framework of Analysis

The understanding of the contributory pension scheme and management of retirement benefits can adequately be appreciated through the Marxian instrumentalist theory as popularized by Ralph Miliband and William Dahhoff (Mc Gowan and Walter, 1984). The theoretical under pinning provides for analytic insights to the surprises as to why the state has continued despite odds to serve the interest of the capitalists in the society. However, the theory contends that contrary to the conventional wisdom that the state is an unbiased power broker in relations to the interest of capital and labour, the sustainer of social contract, the state in the capitalist society has basically function to foster pressure and defend the capitalist accumulation and profits (Asobie, 1990).

However, the ruling class owns and controls the means of production, distribution and exchange and is able by mere virtue of substantial economic power conferred upon it used the state as an instrument for the domination

of society. The performances and functioning of the state has been remoted, strategically positioned through the manipulation by design the state polices and indirectly through the exercise of pressure on the state.

Moreover, according to William Damhoff cited in Gowon and Walker, (1984) examined policy formation from instrumentalist perspective and systematically distinguished the likely processes through which the capitalist class is able to use the state swiftly as an instrument at its will to shape policy in its own interest. These processes include the special interest process, the policy planning among others. As further explained, McGowan and Walter, (1984) maintained that the special interest process entails lobbying the decision makers by the interest groups, including the powerful capitalist class to accept specific policies and general development plans that adequately comprises the state, while the policy planning permits the capitalist class to promotes, protects and at the same rationalizes particular ways of examining reality through the introduction and identification of specific personnel and ideas.

Hence, the centrality and argument of the Marxist instrumentalist theory is that the state has swiftly designed by pursuing the interest of the ruling class in the society rather than the interest of the entire populace as were agreed through the social contract due to the link between the ruling class and the state apparatus. However, initiation and the applicability of the defined benefit and contributory pension scheme in the management of retirement benefits of staff of the University is therefore explained in the context of the Marxist instrumentalist theory. The shiftability from defined benefit scheme otherwise known as Pay As You Go (PAYG) to Contributory Pension Scheme is an open attempt by the state to absolve and at the same abdicate its fundamental responsibility of providing social needs and safety nets to the retired staff and provide pool of cheap funds for capitalist investors through privatization of pension scheme emerged in the face of the inability of the state to meet its pension obligation to the retirees under its defined benefit scheme (Amoo, 2008; Onyeonoru, Egharegba and Imhonopi, 2013; Odo, Igbeka and Ani, 2011).

However, the application of the new contributory pension scheme ensures that the risks associated with pension management and pension administration are shifted to the individuals whose pension funds are housed in a Retirement Savings Account (RSA), funded by both the individual and the employer and managed by a private Pension Funds Administrator. Under the new scheme, gratuity is abolished and systematically replaced with a lump-sum which is not more than 50% of fund in Retirement Savings Account (RSA). At the retirement, pension for life is abolished as monthly pension is calculated based on life expectancy (PRA, 2004:34). Appreciably the new contributory pension scheme systematically exempted the elites (members of the judiciary, members of the military and secret services, University professors) in the society from the scheme by providing that these categories of people retire with their salary for life (PRA, 2004). All these combined together clearly portrays that the contributory pension scheme which was introduced swiftly and purposely serves the interest of the ruling capitalists who aim to increase accumulation of surplus by reducing fund spent by the state on pension payments for the masses and to make adequate available cheap funds which can be utilized by the capitalist class for investment reasons for their selfish aggrandizement.

3. The Voluntary Pension Contributions and Welfare of Retirees

Conventionally, the Nigerian Pension Reform Act of 2004 is a complete variant of the Chilean model of contributory pension system introduced in that country in 1981. The new pension system was a product of a deliberate design to transfer the core responsibilities of the state to her citizens. It was in lieu of the idea that the Nigerian policy makers capitalized that if the country could initiate contributory pension reform, it would yield same benefits for the state as they saw it having produced gains for Chilean government. However, it is important to underscore that by the time Nigerian government has determined and giving serious attention to pension reforms, the Chilean model of pension scheme has started attracting myriad criticisms. The World Bank had come to recognize that Chilean – like reforms had not always delivered the needed benefits that it had initially proclaimed, that too many assumptions have been made and that other reforms were also required that at best complement or even preceded pension reforms (Gill, Pachard and Yermo, 2005; Holzman and Hinz,

2005; World Bank, 2005). The perceived dissatisfaction with the system in terms of its costs and failure to make adequate provision for many of the old had been a persistent theme of the 2005 – 2006 Chilean presidential elections (Casey and Dostal, 2011).

However, appreciating it the more, the Nigerian idea of contributory pension reforms is traceable to early 1997 as an off shoot of the vision 2010 project under which the then military government charged a team to chart the needed goals to be reached by the 50th Anniversary of her independence. One of the objectives was that by the year 2010, most Nigerians shall have access to some form of social protections offered by the state. In Nigeria, the analysis of how compulsorily individuals fund pensions might affect national savings. Using funded pensions to developed the Nigerian financial market to provide long term funding for productive investments and higher growth in the future is an experiment rather than a pre-condition for development in the present.

Furthermore, the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria Sectional (1) sub-section(1), provides for a contributory pension scheme for the payment of retirement benefits of employees to whom the scheme applies. The scheme is contributory because, section (9) sub-section(1) provides that employers and employees in both the public and private sectors (enterprises having five or more employees) shall contribute a minimum of seven and half percent of the employee salary to the scheme. In the case of the military, the government shall contribute a minimum of twelve and half percent while the employees shall contribute a minimum of two and half percent.

However, in the University administration, it is the responsibility of the Personnel department of the institution to issue out employment letter to every staff of the university and at the time maintains a progressive reports and records on every staff. This means that it knows when a staff is or should be due for retirement except in the cases of voluntary or compulsory retirement due to ill-health and expulsion. The process of retirement and payment of final benefits start when the personnel department writes to prospective retiree giving him or her three months' notice to wind down activities including his or her annual leaves. The retiring staff will then proceed to the departments and units indicated on the leaving service form for them to verify whether he or she is indebted to the university. The retiring officer will also apply to the personnel emolument unit of the bursary through the bursar to prepare and send his or her last pay certificate to the personnel services department and pension unit to enable them complete his form and compute his final benefits. The Bursar in turn endorses the documents to the pension manager for necessary actions.

4. Assessment of the contributory pension scheme

The reappraisal of the contributory pension scheme is ethically aimed at addressing the inadequacies of the public pension scheme hitherto practiced in Nigeria. Following various Committees like Dr. Fika ,Dr. Aboki Zhawa and Mallam Nasir El Rufai, they all recommended the contributory pension schemes. However, no matter the rationale behind the introduction of the contributory pension scheme, what is vital from its introduction and adoption is to cater for the retirees. In order to be financially independent at retirement, every individual must adequately be conscious about not only how he can make money at the present, but should also think of how the money made at present can be systematically be utilized to keep growing at old age when the individual concerned may be willing to work but the body will be weak.

Moreover, the underlying benefits from the introduction of the contributory pension scheme in the public sectors are:

- a. Every individual employee is entitled to an account known as Retirement Savings Account upon which payments are made and he/she has the right to withdraw money from it.
- b. There are tendencies for the Pensioner to earn more from his Retirement Savings Account from the interests that accrue to him.
- c. The conventional wisdom that not everybody can save or the poor habits for savings by the civil servants' due partly to poor salaries are reduced.

- d. However, on the other part of the government, it reduces the burden of pension fund on her, thereby shifting it to Pension Administrators. Also, Contributory Pension Scheme makes available investable funds to the government. The investments if properly managed will help to boost the economy of the country.

In assessing the features of the contributory pension scheme, Aborisade (2012) outlined the fundamental features of the scheme as were encapsulated in the Pension Reform Act, 2014 (Now PLA, 2014) to include privatization of the pension system through decentralized institutionalization of managing individual retirement accounts by privately owned Pension Funds Administrators (PFA), abolition of payments of gratuity and absence of guaranteed pension for life. On the basis of this, the goal of the new scheme is to roll back the state and halt it from abdicating its social responsibilities.

Similarly, Imhanlahimi and Idolor, (2011) noted that the Contributory Pension Scheme is adequately plagued with insufficient investment returns because most contributors have found that their assess yields no returns in investments. By implication, the PFAs grow richer at the expense of the pensioners because while the commissions for the PFAs are guaranteed, the returns on investments for the contributors are left to the vagaries of market forces. This is a serious contradiction with the advantages of the defined benefits scheme which tends to redistributes incomes from the rich to the poor.

Moreover, in another related empirical study, Imhanlhim and Idolor, (2011) set out to investigate the impact of Contributory Pension Scheme on the workers' productivity. The findings revealed that 45% of the respondents preferred the old pension scheme while only 35% preferred the new scheme. It is noted that workers or retirees were not adequately satisfied with their level of involvements in the decision-making process of the contributory pension scheme. It is argued that the values of the new pension scheme are more favorable to the government than the workers and retirees.

However, Siyan, (2008) in his assessments and contributions contends that the fundamental and primary objective of the contributory pension scheme is to ensure that every pensioner who worked either in the private or public sector receives his or her retirement benefits as at when due. This is concerned with establishing a system that would ensure that workers or pensioners receive benefits by their own savings and not to depend on the government subsidies. The Contributory Pension Scheme is remarkable for establishing sustainable, simple and transparent system. It also established effective, regulatory and supervisory framework. It is believed that the contributory pension scheme will not only eliminate the perennial problems of pension schemes but will enable government to borrow from the accumulated funds with interests.

5. Conditionalities and Eligibility for Gratuity and Pension

In Nigeria, pensions and gratuities at prescribed rate are payable to an officer(s) when one of the following occurs

- (i) If an officer who has served for ten years (10) or more retires or withdraws from public services, his or her pension shall not be paid until he or she attains forty five (45) years of age.
- (ii) If a properly constituted medical Board shall pronounces an officer unsuitable for continuity of his or her services based on health challenges
- (iii) If due to re-organization and the incumbent officer(s) cannot be offered suitable alternative post, he or she shall be called to retire or withdraw from the service. In this case, the officer shall be entitled to a ten (10) percent increase of their pension and gratuity as com-pension for premature retirement.
- (iv) Under the compulsory retirement, the officer is required to withdraw or retire from service by the government in the interest of the public. In respect to the compulsory retirement, if an officer had spent five (5) years but less than ten (10) years, he or she will be entitled to only gratuity and if he or she had spent ten (10) years and above in the service, he or she will be qualified for both pension and gratuity.

- (v) If an officer who has completed ten (10) years or more in public service dies in the service, his registered next of kin or designated survivor will be entitled to gratuity in addition to pension the deceased officer would have earned if he or she had retired.
- (vi) If an officer who is holding a temporal or contract appointment transfers to a permanent one, the period he or she was on temporal or contract appointment will count in full for the purpose of calculating his or her pension and gratuity.
- (vii) Payment of Retirement Benefits to employees with mixed services and transfer. Employees with mixed services, are those who rendered public service in more than one establishment. In this situation, the pension and gratuity that accrue to them from their former employment have transfer value which will be paid up to date of transfer to their new employers by their former employers if they finally retired. (Fapohund, 2013; Dalang, 2006; Akhiojemi, 2007 and Ahmed; 2011)

6. Departments and Units that Handle Retirement and Pension in the University

The University like every other organizations is systematically organized in its day to day activities. like other public institutions, the university with its humanistic elements has various units and departments that handle and foster the relationship that exists between it and her employees. The following units in different departments are involved either in the retirements of staff, preparing of settlement papers, auditing and payment of gratuities and pensions.

i. Personnel Services Department

In any organization, be it public or private, the Human Resources Department cannot be over emphasized. However, for effective and efficient pension administration, the Record unit of the Personnel Services Department acts as the registry and keeps the files and records of all the staff from recruitment to their retirement. The personnel services department under the leadership, supervision and coordination of the comptroller, is in-charge of appointment, placement, development, discipline and retirement of staff.

However, the records of service of every Establishment's staff contain vital information on the names of the members of the staff, date of birth, date of appointment, marital status, next-of-kin, educational qualifications etc. The Records unit of the Personnel Services Department always peruses its records and make a list of staff who are due for retirement and consequent upon, issues out three (3) months' notice of disengagement letter informing them to start winding down their activities in the University. It also informs the pension unit through the Bursar that a staff is retiring and subsequently instructs it to compute the retiree's final benefits and pay him or her accordingly and recover any indebtedness if it occurred.

ii. The Bursary Department

The Bursary department is the spinning point of pension administration and payments in the University. It is headed by a Deputy Bursar as the pension manager who is under the supervision of the Bursar but responsible and accountable to the pension Board of Trustees and the University council.

iii. The University Pension Board of Trustees

Following the Federal Government directives through the circular; PEN.92/38/8.28/195 of 1997, the Universities are to set up a Pension Board of Trustee in their respective institutions to ensure regular payments of retirement benefits to retirees. However, the circular charged the University Board of Trustees with the following responsibilities

- (a) To determine the pension funds for their schemes using actual valuation.
- (b) To determine the investment portfolios in which to move pension funds.
- (c) To appoint under writers and insurance brokers after clearance with the Establishment and Management Services.

- (d) To be responsible for the payment of retirement benefits to retirees and assisted by Insurance broker consultants.
- (e) The Board of Trustees shall submit their annual budget proposal for pension funds to the office of Establishment and Management Services for approval
- (f) The budget office shall base its annual budgetary allocation of funds to the parastatals on the above approval
- (g) The Board of Trustees shall render account on a quarterly basis to the office of Establishment and Management Services
- (h) Funds should be released directly to the Boards of Trustees by the budget office quarterly on the recommendation of the office Establishment and Management Service.

However, the University Pension Board of Trustees membership is composed of the following:

- (a) The Vice-Chancellor (Chairman)
- (b) The Bursar
- (c) The Registrar
- (d) The Librarian
- (e) The Comptroller
- (f) The Pension Manager (secretary)
- (g) A Representative of each of the following staff unions of the university.
 - (i) Academics Staff Union of Universities (ASUU)
 - (ii) Senior Staff Association of Nigerian Universities (SSANU)
 - (iii) Non- Academic Staff Union of Nigeria Universities (NASU)

(h) Representatives of the Federal Military of Education, Federal Office of Establishment and Management Services and National Insurance Corporation of Nigeria (NICON).

Conclusion and Recommendations

By reconciling pension and old age, the former becomes an essential form of social security and safety nets for the later. This is so because retirement and old age is a must and inevitable for every employee and this underscores the urgent need for a sustainable pension program which will holistically serves as a form of social security against the likely unknown and challenges of retirement in old age.

However, arising the foregoing, the paper adequately recommends the following for policy implementation:

- i. That a comprehensive accounting standard for retirement benefits must be put in place to adequately protect the pension fund. Also, government should provide a relatively safe and less volatile area in the pension funds which can be invested with consumerate returns assured to the beneficiaries.
- ii. The right to gratuity should be restored and calculated on the basis of years in service. This should be paid directly to the employees by the employers upon retirement to avoid the current situation where benefits are subject to management and processing fee by the Pension Fund Administrators (PEAs)
- iii. There must be intensified public awareness and enlightenment in the new scheme. There are lots of misinformation and ignorance and government needs to demonstrate strong political will and support thereby enhancing relevant legal framework to be put in place.
- iv. With the recent reform Act of 2014, public servants should retire with eight percent of their salaries as obtained under the old scheme. Also, pension should be paid for life and not calculated on the basis of life expectancy.

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